

ASSESSMENT OF MATERIAL COMPOSITION AND COLOR DISTRIBUTION IN POST-CONSUMER POLYPROPYLENE BALES

Hannah Zeilinger, Joerg Fischer

Johannes Kepler University Linz, Institute of Polymeric Materials and Testing & LIT Factory, Linz,
Austria

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17302001
hannah.zeilinger@jku.at

Abstract: *In order to meet the recycling targets according to the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) within a circular economy framework, a comprehensive understanding of the input stream is essential. The input stream for plastic waste recycling, commonly delivered as compressed plastic bales, vary in composition and quality due to the heterogeneous composition of the stream. These bales contain the targeted polymer fraction as well as amounts of foreign polymer contaminants and non-plastic contaminants that significantly influence the recycling process and recyclate quality. This study focused on rigid post-consumer polypropylene (PP) bales, assessing both material composition and color. PP is one of the most commonly used polymers in consumer packaging. The bales consist of food packaging, such as yoghurt cups, ice cream, or butter containers as well as non-food packaging, such as flower pots. The input materials, processed into shredded flakes, were sorted by material type using a portable near-infrared (NIR) sensor. The flakes were divided into rigid polymers, including PP, polyethylene, polystyrene, and polyamide as well as flexible polymers, aluminum, non-detectable components (e.g., black particles), and other materials (e.g., wood). Moreover, the rigid PP fraction was manually classified by color (transparent, white, red, green, and blue). The study showed that 80-90% of the investigated input samples consist of rigid polypropylene. Color sorting revealed that approximately 40 % of the rigid PP fraction was transparent. White rigid PP comprised around 30%. A detailed analysis of the plastic input stream enables an optimized recycling process that leads to an improved recyclate quality and reduced material loss. This supports regulatory compliance and enhances overall recycling efficiency and sustainability.*

Keywords: plastic waste, polypropylene, mechanical recycling, sorting, material composition, color

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for sustainability and circular economy concepts to achieve the recycling targets have intensified the focus on viable end-of-life strategies for post-consumer plastics. The largest end-use market for plastics in the EU27+3 is represented by packaging, accounting for nearly 60 % of the total plastic waste. Polypropylene is the second most used plastic after polyethylene for packaging applications (Plastics Europe, 2022; European Commission, 2018). A common method to recycle plastic waste is mechanical recycling. Typical mechanical recycling steps include sorting, shredding, washing, drying, and extrusion of the collected plastic waste into recyclates (Friedrich, 2019; Brouwer, 2020). The quality of the input waste stream plays a crucial role in effective recycling processes. Quality differences and inconsistencies like a heterogeneous composition and contamination of the input waste streams limit the processability and the subsequent applications of mechanically recycled

materials. The presence of even small amounts of foreign polymers or non-plastic contaminants can significantly impair the performance and appearance of recyclates. Therefore, sorting and separation is an essential step to generate a homogenous and clear input to produce high-quality recyclates (Al-Salem, 2009). Sorting can be done on object-level and on flake-level, based on different criteria such as material composition, shape, density, color, size, or application. Common sorting techniques include manual sorting, and automated sorting (e.g., near-infrared (NIR) spectrometry, wind sifting, and density separation). Near-infrared is one of the most widely used methods for sorting plastics. However, NIR has a few limitations. As it is an optical surface technique, any obstruction - such as labels, sleeves, overlapping products, or dirt - can cause false readings. Furthermore, multilayered plastics, flexibles (i.e., films) or black particles cannot be accurately identified or are not at all identifiable by NIR (Ragaert, 2017; Akhras, 2024; Hahladakis, 2019). Although plastic films (two-dimensional (2D)) are recyclable, their low bulk density limits the efficiency in sorting and mechanical reprocessing compared to rigid, three-dimensional (3D), plastics (e.g., hollow bodies) (Hahladakis, 2019; Feil, 2020). Sorting by material composition is important to remove foreign polymeric and non-polymeric contaminations, as their presence can lead to immiscibility and incompatibility issues affecting the mechanical and thermal properties of the recycled products. Furthermore, color sorting is essential, since colorants can also cause problems during plastics recycling and influence aesthetic, mechanical, and thermal properties. No color sorting usually results in dark green, brown, or grey colored products with a lower quality, limiting further applications (Akhras, 2024; Cucuzza, 2023). This study focuses on the analysis of rigid post-consumer polypropylene waste bales on flake-level to gain insight into the composition and color distribution of the input stream. These two indicators should provide an estimation of the quality of a rigid post-consumer polypropylene waste stream used in an industrial polypropylene mechanical recycling plant.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and pre-treatment

Pre-sorted rigid PP bales, containing post-consumer food and non-food packaging waste, were provided by PreZero Polymers Austria GmbH. Among others, the bales included yoghurt cups, ice cream, butter/margarine pots, meat packages, microwave-proof containers, and flower pots. As a first step, the bales were mechanically shredded into flakes and used as input material for a mechanical recycling process of the industrial mechanical recycling plant. To gain representative insight into the composition of the input stream, a total of six samples were taken post-shredding from the recycling line at intervals of approximately 30 minutes. The flakes were washed at 20 °C for 15 min using an industrial washing machine (Miele & Cie. KG, Gütersloh, Germany). Additionally, a separation from higher-density materials via a swim-sink tank with water at room temperature was done. After the washing and separation step, the samples were dried at 60 °C for 3 h in a drying chamber (Binder GmbH, Tuttlingen, Germany). Furthermore, the flakes were sieved with a vibration sieve shaker (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) to remove all particles with a size of 1 mm or smaller. Pre-treatment of the flakes was necessary to replicate key steps of the washing process during mechanical recycling in order to remove surface contaminants to enable a more accurate analysis.

2.2 Methods

Material-based sorting of the pre-treated flakes was conducted to determine the composition of the six samples. Flake classification was carried out using a portable NIR hand-sensor (trinamiX GmbH, Ludwigshafen, Germany) to assign them to distinct material categories. The flakes were sorted into rigid polymers (3D), specifically PP, polyethylene (PE), polystyrene (PS), and polyamide (PA). Further categories included films, aluminum, non-detectable flakes (primarily black particles), and other materials (e.g., wood). Due to the above-mentioned limitations of NIR regarding multilayered plastics and flexibles, no classification of the film fraction was done. Each material category was weighed and expressed as a percentage of the total mass of the corresponding sample. The rigid PP fraction was

additionally analyzed to evaluate the color distribution. For this purpose, five color categories (transparent, white, red, green, and blue) were defined and the PP flakes were manually sorted based on these classifications. The individual color fractions were also weighed and expressed in mass percent.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Material composition

The material composition of the flake samples of the six investigated input fractions is depicted in Figure 1 and the exact percentages of the composition analysis are summarized in Table 1. As expected, the PP content dominates in all samples analyzed.

Figure 8: Material composition of the investigated post-consumer rigid PP bales.

The results displayed that rigid PP comprises between 80 and 90% of the total flake mass in all six samples. Minor fractions of PE, PS, and PA are also present, albeit in significantly lower portions. PE constantly contributes approximately 1-3 %, with PS and PA being even less abundant. These polymers can be considered as impurities in PP dominant streams. Films represent the second highest share in the compositions ranging from 6% to nearly 13%. Flexibles also impede plastics recycling and lower the quality of the end-products. Aluminum and materials labeled as "not detected" and "others" constitute very small percentages of the overall sample composition. The presence of all these contaminants impacts the processability and quality of the recycled material if not removed. The non-PP fractions, although in small amounts, highlight the need for effective sorting before entering the recycling process and separation during the process to ensure high-quality PP recyclates.

Table 7: Overview on the detailed material composition of the investigated post-consumer rigid PP bales

	PP [%]	PE [%]	PS [%]	PA [%]	Films [%]	Aluminum [%]	not detected [%]	Others [%]
Sample 1	80.2	1.1	0.7	0.3	12.7	0.8	0.9	3.3
Sample 2	84.9	2.2	0.7	0.2	9.1	0.4	0.9	1.9
Sample 3	86.6	2.0	1.0	0.1	7.3	0.2	0.6	2.2
Sample 4	87.5	2.5	0.6	0.1	6.3	0.5	1.3	1.2
Sample 5	86.3	3.0	1.7	0.0	6.0	0.6	0.7	1.8
Sample 6	85.2	2.2	1.4	0.2	8.9	0.4	0.3	1.4

3.2 Color distribution

Figure 2 illustrates the color distribution of the six rigid PP flake samples, which is a crucial parameter for evaluating the functional and aesthetic suitability of recyclates in high-quality applications. Across all samples, two color categories dominate: transparent and white.

Figure 9: Color distribution of the investigated post-consumer rigid PP fraction.

Transparent flakes consistently contribute the largest fraction, ranging from roughly 38% to slightly over 45%. White flakes represent the second most abundant category, accounting for approximately 30-35%. Together, these two categories comprise more than 70% of the total flake volume in all samples. Colored flakes appear in smaller, yet non-negligible, proportions. Green flakes range from 6.6% to 9.3%. Blue flakes contribute between 9.8% and nearly 15.0%, with sample 5 showing the highest share. Red flakes make up the smallest share, with percentages between 4.4% and 6.3%. Transparent and white flakes are favorable for recycling processes since they enable a broader range of recoloring or direct reuse in higher-performance products. In contrast, strongly pigmented flakes limit the recycling and aesthetic flexibility of the recyclates and restrict end-use options.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of a rigid polypropylene input waste stream revealed that even though PP is the dominant polymer in the sample set, minor fractions of other polymers and non-polymeric contaminants were present. These non-PP fractions, even in small amounts, negatively influence the processability and recyclate properties, if not eliminated during mechanical recycling using sorting and separation techniques. The level and distribution of foreign polymeric and non-polymeric contaminants can vary due to seasonal fluctuations or suppliers. Although material composition and color distribution may vary within a single supplier, greater variability is expected when sourcing from multiple suppliers. Color sorting showed transparent and white flakes make up the largest share, but their desirable advantages are diminished by the presence of colored flakes. This color variability not only results in a darker end-color and a restricted reusability of the recycled material but also downgrades recyclability, mechanical and thermal properties and complicates sorting processes due to poor detectability of dark pigment with NIR spectroscopy. The results underline that accurate knowledge of the input stream is important for tailoring and optimizing the mechanical recycling process. This study highlights the necessity of thorough sorting of post-consumer plastic waste to ensure a consistent and homogenous input stream for mechanical recycling. The production of high-quality secondary raw materials requires

sorting not only by material but also by color, combining object-based sorting with flake-based sorting. Material and color purities contribute significantly to the economic and functional viability of recycled plastic and are crucial for realizing the PPWR recycling targets.

Acknowledgments: *The authors acknowledge financial support from the COMET Centre CHASE, funded within the COMET – Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies program by the BMIMI, the BMWET and the Federal Provinces of Upper Austria and Vienna. The COMET program is managed by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG). Additionally, we would like to thank PreZero Polymers Austria GmbH for the support and for providing the materials used in this study.*

5 REFERENCES

Akhras, M.H., Fischer, J. (2024) Influence of color sorting on the property profile of polyethylene recyclates. AIP Conf. Proc., 3158, 120001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0207901>.

Al-Salem, S.M, Lettieri, P., Baeyens, J. (2009) Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW): a review. Waste Management, 29, 2625-2643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.06.004>.

Brouwer, M.T., Thoden van Velzen, E.U., Ragaert, K, ten Klooster, R. (2020) Technical limits in circularity for plastic packages. Sustainability, 12(23), 10021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122310021>.

Cucuzza, P., Serranti, S., Capabianco, G., Bonifazi, G. (2023) Multi-level color classification of post-consumer plastic packaging flakes by hyperspectral imaging for optimizing the recycling process. Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy, 302, 123157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2023.123157>.

European Commission (2018) A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. EUR-Lex - 52018DC0028 - EN - EUR-Lex (last accessed: 06.08.2025).

Feil, A., Pretz, T. (2020) Mechanical recycling of packaging waste. Plastic Waste and Recycling, chapter 11, 283-319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817880-5.00011-6>.

Friedrich, K., Möllnitz, S., Holzschuster, S., Pomberger, R., Sarc, R. (2019) Benchmark analysis for plastic recyclates in Austrian waste management. Detritus, 9, 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.31025/2611-4135/2019.13869>.

Hahladakis, J.N., Iacovidou, E. (2019) An overview of the challenges and trade-offs in closing the loop of post-consumer plastic waste (PCPW): focus on recycling. Journal of Hazardous Materials, 380, 120887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.120887>.

Plastics Europe (2022) Plastics - the Facts 2022. <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-facts-2022/> (last accessed: 07.08.2025).

Ragaert, K., Delva, L., Van Geem, K. (2017) Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste. Waste Management, 69, 24-58. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044>.